
Worten – An Analysis of the Organizational Structure

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ABSTRACT: Worten was chosen as the object of study due to its recognition in the national and international market, as well as the ease of access to information. This project aims to deepen the understanding of the organizational structure of a successful company, highlighting the importance of rigorous strategic planning, essential for the effective alignment between operational management and strategic management.

The collection of information was based on credible and diverse sources, such as journalistic articles and materials available on Worten's official website, providing a complete overview of the company's management processes.

KEYWORDS: Worten; Strategy; SWOT; Leadership.

INTRODUCTION

Management is an essential pillar for the success of organizations, supported by four fundamental functions: planning, organization, direction and control. These functions are interconnected to create a consistent system that helps in the decisions and actions necessary to achieve the objectives set by managers.

Planning is the main step in the entire process, as it is where the objectives and strategies needed to achieve them are defined. This stage answers questions such as who is responsible for each task, how they will be carried out and what resources will be used. It also allows the “workforce” to be identified, and essential materials, as well as grouping individuals around specific goals.

Once a plan has been defined, organization follows, which aims to transform ideas and strategies into concrete actions. At this stage, tasks are distributed, relationships are established between team members and leadership is assigned to people responsible for coordinating efforts.

Next, management plays a key role in implementing what has been planned and organized. It is up to managers to lead their teams, motivating them and ensuring that everyone works towards achieving common goals.

Finally, the control function comes into play to monitor the previous steps, ensuring that the objectives are being met and that any adjustments are made.

COMPANY PRESENTATION

1.1 COMPANY CREATION AND HISTORICAL MILESTONES

Worten's trajectory has been a milestone of achievements and innovations since its foundation. Over the years, important milestones have been achieved that reflect the company's commitment to excellence and evolution in the market.

To give a historical overview of Worten, it is important to note that the first store opened in 1996, in the city of Chaves. Since then, the brand has won several awards that have reinforced its reputation and credibility in the market for the sale of various products. Among the awards won, distinctions such as “Consumer's Choice”, “Product of the Year” and “Trusted Brand” stand out (Ferreira, 2023).

In 2001, Worten took a significant step forward by launching its online store, simplifying the consumer experience and eliminating the need to physically visit stores to make purchases. In 2007, the brand underwent its first rebranding and, nine years later, in 2016, a new update was presented, resulting in the logo that the brand uses to this day.

Another important milestone was the launch, in 2018, of the Worten Marketplace, a virtual platform that allows partner companies to sell their products directly to consumers.

In recent years, Worten has strengthened its presence with omnichannel strategies, combining the physical and digital worlds, in addition to investing in new market segments, such as beauty, sports and DIY. It recently stood out for the acquisition of companies such as iServices (2019) and Zaask (2021), expanding the range of services, especially in repairs and digital solutions.

Worten – An Analysis of the Organizational Structure

1.2 FORM LEGAL, SECTOR OF ACTIVITY AND PRODUCTS SOLD

Worten, a public limited company with a share capital of 21,530,000 euros, is a reference in the trade and retail sector, operating both in physical stores and on the digital platform. The company sells a wide variety of products, including new, used and refurbished items, and also provides services such as installation, repair and home delivery. In addition, it offers optional insurance, allowing customers greater security when purchasing and using products.

Worten stands out for its wide range of products, covering a range of categories, such as household appliances, IT, telecommunications, gaming, books and culture, home and decoration, health and childcare, sports and leisure. In addition, it offers financing solutions to facilitate purchases, frequent promotional campaigns and a flexible returns policy, aiming to provide a convenient shopping experience adapted to the needs of consumers.

The company also invests in sustainability, encouraging the recycling of electronic equipment and providing refurbished products, thus promoting a more circular economy (Moreira, 2018).

1.3 COMPANY GEOGRAPHICAL LOCATION

Worten's headquarters are currently located at Avenida Vítor Figueiredo, No. 4, in the J World Trade Center, in Carnaxide, Oeiras. The brand operates over 180 stores in Portugal, as well as a physical store in Madrid and 15 in the Canary Islands. After the decision to sell 17 stores to MediaMarkt and close another 14 in Spain, Worten chose to focus mainly on the Portuguese market and the Spanish island regions, where it has invested most actively (see appendix 1).

Based on information taken from an article published on February 8, 2022, by idealista, Worten intended to open eight to ten stores in the year in question. Sonae, the group that owns Worten and many other companies, intended to expand the business and broaden the diversification of the offer to customers. In addition to opening physical stores, the objective was also to strengthen online sales on the Marketplace, which accounted for 10% of sales in 2020 and "close to 20%" in 2021.

In terms of revenue, we chose to look for reports and studies already carried out, based on a study by Ana Filipa Sousa Moreira in 2018 on Business Valuation, with Sonae SGPS, SA as the case study, for the University of Aveiro as part of the Master's degree in Finance (2018, p.50). The author of the project shows a table with some figures on Worten's sales between 2013 and 2017 and the company's forecast for the following years. Worten's sales in 2016 and 2017 were €910M and €1003M, respectively. Sonae predicted an increase in Worten's sales over the next five years, with an estimated revenue of €1024M in 2018 and €1167M in 2022.

Based on the news published by SIC Notícias, Worten achieved the estimated objectives in 2017, reaching 1.2 billion euros.

Another report prepared by Sonae and published by them states that in 2020, Worten's sales tripled from January to August, thus doubling the brand's online market share. According to data from Markttest, more than 1.5 million Portuguese people visit the platform every month. The Marketplace alone is responsible for around 20% of total online sales in Portugal, with more than 1,100 sellers.

1.4 COMPETITION

In the market in which it operates, Worten faces strong competition from other companies in the same sector, with Fnac, MediaMarkt and Rádio Popular standing out as its main competitors.

Fnac, a direct competitor of Worten, established itself in Portugal in 1998, with the opening of its first store in the Colombo Center, in Lisbon. Since then, the French brand has won several awards that reinforce its prestige, such as "The Best Store Portugal 2021/22", "Marketing Media and Advertising Award 2020" and "Choice of Excellence Award 2020".

MediaMarkt arrived on the Portuguese market in 2004 and stood out for its innovative marketing strategies, such as the introduction of the famous "VAT-Free Day" and the slogan "I'm not a fool". In addition, the company was a pioneer in promoting Black Friday in Portugal, bringing with it a more aggressive and competitive approach to promotional campaigns.

Rádio Popular, in turn, is a national brand that focuses mainly on home appliances, consumer electronics and technology. With a competitive pricing policy and a well-distributed network of stores, it manages to attract customers, especially outside of large metropolitan areas.

To stand out in such a competitive market, Worten has implemented several strategies to win over and retain customers. One of its initiatives is its "best price guarantee" policy, which promises to match the price of a product if the customer finds a lower offer on previously selected online markets that meet certain criteria.

In addition, Worten offers free home delivery on selected purchases, a measure that aims to provide a good customer experience, eliminating the need for travel and making the purchasing process more accessible.

The company also invests in loyalty initiatives, such as points programs, exclusive promotions for registered customers and partnerships with other brands. Additionally, after-sales service is an area in which Worten seeks to stand out, by offering specialized technical assistance, equipment repair and extended warranties.

Worten – An Analysis of the Organizational Structure

2. PLANNING

Worten's mission is to "bring the best technology to everyone, without exception, today and always." The brand is committed to being close to its customers, offering low prices, personalized service and a wide variety of products and services, always with the aim of meeting the customer's needs and expectations. In this way, Worten values service and prioritizes customer satisfaction.

Worten has been investing in an omnichannel strategy to facilitate communication between customers and employees. With the customer number, employees can access information about the customer's last interaction with Worten, reducing service time and eliminating the need for the customer to repeat their problem.

This aims to provide a uniform experience, whether online or in person.

In its marketing, Worten once again chose Ricardo Araújo Pereira as the face of the company, maintaining a humorous tone and reinforcing the idea that Worten "has everything and more". This campaign aims to show that Worten is the solution for everyone, who leads full lives and balances several facets of their lives, as professionals, parents, children, partners and passionate about various hobbies.

In an interview with the website Ecommerce News Portugal, António Fuzeta explained that Worten's strategic preparation for Black Friday begins many months before November, with a multidisciplinary team. The Head of Brand and Communication highlighted that all the work is the result of a clear definition of the value proposition, strengthening of logistics and consistent communication between all channels. Product prices are reviewed in comparison with the market to offer the best promotions to customers. Digital marketing is adjusted to be in line with market trends.

Worten aims to become a one-stop shop for Portuguese consumers, where customers know they will find everything they need without having to compare prices or quality with other brands. The focus is clearly on online, with a focus on the shopping experience, convenience and level of service in each delivery, in order to attract new consumers.

We conducted an internal and external analysis of the organization. In the SWOT analysis, the brand's focus on offering the best prices, constantly studying the market, stood out as its strengths. Investment in marketing is also a strong point, with slogans that have gained recognition among the Portuguese, such as "Our strength is price" and "Worten has everything and more". These details make all the difference to customers. The increase in the number of stores to serve all Portuguese people also helps to establish Worten as the number 1 brand in the sector in Portugal.

In terms of weaknesses, that is, the company's weaknesses, Worten may fall behind when it comes to product diversity. Although the brand claims to offer 6 million products in various categories, it is surpassed by Fnac, which claims to offer a total of 8 million products, according to information on the respective companies' websites.

We can also highlight the company's opportunities and how they impact the market. Worten's main focus is on seasonal marketing campaigns, such as Black Friday and Christmas, which represent a large part of the company's revenue.

Regarding threats, that is, the threats that the company faces, as already mentioned in more detail, competition from Fnac, MediaMarkt and Rádio Popular are the main challenges that Worten needs to overcome to stand out as the most innovative, up-to-date and the one that offers the best prices and the best quality.

Regarding external analysis, which inevitably influences the company's progress and may change the way it enters the market, we understand that, although we have not found anything on the subject because it is relatively recent, the resignation of our Prime Minister António Costa has shaken the entire political, economic, social and technological situation in our country, affecting, of course, people and companies like Worten in all areas. Doubts are being raised about government investments, the lifestyle of the Portuguese in the face of political instability, unemployment levels, which are a serious problem in our country, interest rates that have been increasing over the months, in May 2023 reaching 4% for the first time in 11 years for housing loans and for deposits the average rate rose to 1.26%, the highest value in 8 years.

Therefore, all this crisis and instability surrounding Worten has changed its stance in relation to the market.

3. ORGANIZATION AND ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

On the Worten website it was not possible to find an image that clearly defined the size and the entire structure and hierarchies of the company, but we were still able to find the Worten Management Team, which is made up of:

Miguel Mota Freitas, Board Member & Chief Executive Officer (CEO) - with a degree in Economics from FEP, he also trained at AESE Business School, a senior management program for companies and, in 2010, the Advanced Management Program Lisbon & Chicago.

Mário Pereira, Board Member & Chief Operating Officer (COO) - he also graduated in Economics from the University of Porto. He then completed a Masters at the Universidade Nova de Lisboa, earning a Master of Business Administration (MBA). He followed the same path as his colleague and went to AESE Business School in 2000. He also attended Harvard where he studied The General Management Program, Strategy and Management.

Paulo Simões, Board Member & Chief Financial Officer (CFO) - Paulo received the award for best student of the year and graduated in Biotechnology from Universidade Nova de Lisboa, where he also completed his Masters in General Management. He completed his academic career in 2004, also at Harvard University, in Executive Education, The General Management Program.

Worten – An Analysis of the Organizational Structure

Worten, with the aim of getting closer to its customers, has created a place on its website where anyone can search for “Testimonials”, as the brand calls them, and meet some of its employees. We have, therefore, the Operations Director, Danilo Vieira, who is now responsible for being the Regional Sales Director of the stores in Greater Lisbon and Madeira. The company's Marketing Director, António Fuzeta, as mentioned above. Manuel Almeida, responsible for the Worten Resolve area and lastly Inês Castanheira, Project Manager Coordinator - Supply Chain.

Unfortunately, it was not possible to find a presentation of the company's organizational chart, due to the fact that it has many employees and is very large.

Despite this, we believe that Worten adopts a divisional structure in order to facilitate the work of managers and better distribute functions, so that each department head is able to focus better on their role, increasing effectiveness and efficiency. This is because there are many employees, customers and suppliers to deal with, and this departmentalization requires a separation of all this workload and responsibilities.

We believe that departmentalization is done by geographic areas, customers, products and functions. Thus, responsibility and delegation will also be equally distributed according to hierarchical levels.

The decentralization of authority and responsibilities in a company like Worten is beneficial because of the speed and effectiveness of decisions, since the people responsible are closer to the problem. They will obviously have to be people with character and the trust of their superiors to assume these positions.

4. DIRECTION

Worten uses several strategies and instruments to motivate its employees.

Advantages all year round

- Awarded to employees in Sonae Group badges.

Life and health insurance

- Every employee is entitled to free life and health insurance. Health insurance can be extended to spouses and children.

Mobile phone and communications and data package

- Depending on the role, each employee may have access to a voucher to purchase a mobile phone and a Voice + Data communications plan with special conditions.

Advantages from over 230 partners

- Advantages for our employees in various areas of Fashion and Clothing: gyms and lifestyle; beauty and self-care; optics; education (children and adults) and training; catering; travel; hotels, car rental; health and medicine and telecommunications.

Awards linked to individual and company goals

- Depending on the role, employees have monetary incentives associated with individual and collective goals.

Meal Card Gives

- Employees can choose to receive the lunch subsidy on their meal card

It allows for greater organization.

In addition to these six strategies, Worten also adopts another instrument to motivate employees, which is flexible working, that is, depending on their role, employees have access to a set of flexibility policies (see appendix 2).

The main department responsible for designing and implementing motivation strategies is the Human Resources Operations Department (Ana Luísa Gonçalves) – According to Ana Gonçalves, her job consists of ensuring all Human Resources (HR) processes, starting with recruitment, going through different processes, such as evaluation and social climate, and taking into account all components of team development, from training, motivation, and team well-being (see appendix 3).

“It is a constant challenge, since in this role, I am responsible for the link between Operations and the company's Human Resources strategy.”Ana Luísa Gonçalves

The method by which different motivation strategies are implemented for different groups of employees can be summarized in the following table, which concisely illustrates the approaches adopted for each specific segment of employees.

5. CONTROL

Worten organizes its control system into three main levels: strategic, tactical and operational.

At the strategic level, the focus is on tracking long-term objectives, ensuring they are aligned with the company's vision, mission, and goals. Key performance indicators, also known as KPIs, are used to measure progress toward these goals.

At the tactical level, short- and medium-term activities are monitored, such as departmental performance, project management, and execution of action plans. Managers adjust processes and apply corrective measures whenever necessary, with budget analysis and departmental plans being central elements at this level.

At the operational level, control focuses on day-to-day operations, with a focus on stock management, operational efficiency and quality control. To achieve this, Worten uses the Stock Management tool, which optimizes inventory management, reducing stockouts and enabling rapid transfers between stores.

Worten – An Analysis of the Organizational Structure

Worten also integrates real-time data across information systems, ensuring a comprehensive view of performance. KPIs are defined and monitored at all levels, with regular assessments to identify deviations and implement corrective actions. This approach is reinforced by a culture of continuous improvement, which promotes innovation and adaptation to change.

The company has strict policies in place, including compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), to ensure responsible use of customer information. This information is used to personalize promotions, improve services, and manage repairs. Regarding product returns, Worten has 14 to 15 days for customers to return items in perfect condition. Credit risk is controlled with cash payments and financial analysis tools.

Credit risk is low, as most transactions are made on a cash basis. For the others, customer relationships are managed through a system of collecting financial and qualitative information provided by recognized entities, which assess the viability of customers. This system also identifies the need to use risk mitigation instruments, such as credit insurance, bank guarantees or letters of credit. With regard to suppliers, credit risk may arise from advance payments or outstanding amounts related to commercial revenues. This risk, however, is reduced by the expectation of continuity of the commercial relationship.

In 2018, Worten launched the Digitalism program, which has three main pillars. The first is to improve the customer and employee experience, making it more digital and consistent. The second is to transform data management, eliminating information isolation, enriching it with external sources and automating decisions. The third is to implement new ways of working, with multidisciplinary teams, agile methodologies, promoting autonomy and continuous learning.

The first Digitalism initiatives, with the ORDERs and REPAIRs teams, have had positive results. The goal is to expand this approach to the entire organization, creating a more digital, competitive and customer-centric Worten, balancing technology and the human touch in physical stores.

2018 was also the year in which Worten launched its Marketplace, and expanding its business through the integration of partners reflects a management model focused on the strategic control of the organization. Another reason that led the company to invest in the Marketplace through digital transformation is related to online competitors, as by leveraging the strength of its brand and existing traffic, the organization-maintained control over its competitive position in the market. Worten's performance was supported by the success of the Marketplace and the expansion in the range of services offered, which further strengthened its leadership position in the market. Turnover totaled 1.2 billion euros, a growth of 5.4% compared to 2021. Online sales remain relevant, representing 16% of turnover. Among the countless possible options for transitioning from a traditional business model to a modern business model, the Marketplace was chosen, as it is “the fastest and lightest way from a capital and investment point of view to take this path”, as reported by Joana Pina Pereira, Director of e-commerce at Worten.

Thus, organizational control is implicit in the careful management of resources, the strategic alignment of decisions and the ability to monitor the performance of the Marketplace as a tool for growth and innovation.

Finally, considering the analysis of deviations at Worten, this is carried out periodically, comparing the actual results with the budgeted values. This comparison is made monthly and communicated to those involved in preparing the budget, with the aim of maximizing the motivational impact. Managers identify the points of divergence from the budget and analyze the causes of these discrepancies, allowing the implementation of corrective measures. If the discrepancies are caused by an unrealistic budget or by conditions significantly different from those expected, the budget is reviewed and adjusted.

6. ANALYSIS AND CRITICAL REFLECTION

With this work we intend to provide a more in-depth understanding of Worten, which everyone knows as a renowned company, but few know the story behind its success.

Having said that, we believe that our objective was achieved, considering that we carried out extensive research to be able to respond correctly to everything that was proposed to us. In our view, we carried out a well-structured and organized work, managing to obtain all the data necessary to carry out a complete work.

The work demonstrates clarity in examining management practices, market strategies and challenges faced by the company.

Regarding the results obtained, it was possible to verify that Worten stands out for its efficiency in operational management and innovative marketing strategies. There was an emphasis on the digitalization of processes, which contributed to improving the customer experience. Challenges related to competition and the need for continuous innovation to sustain growth were also highlighted.

Through the analysis of the work, we were able to perceive some interesting and well-conceived things in some of the options taken by the company within each topic, respectively:

Company Creation and Historical Milestones

Worten has seen an evolution marked by innovations, such as the launch of the Marketplace in 2018, which now represents 20% of its online sales. The focus on rebranding and updating the logo reinforces the brand's commitment to modernization and adaptation to the market.

Worten – An Analysis of the Organizational Structure

Legal form, sector of activity and products sold

The company stands out for its wide range of products and services in the trade and retail sector, combining physical and digital operations. The focus on sustainable practices, such as recycling and refurbished products, reflects an approach aligned with current trends.

Geographical location of the company

The consolidated presence in Portugal and the Canary Islands highlights a strategic focus on higher return markets, while maintaining potential for further expansion in the future.

Competition

In the competitive market in which it operates, Worten stands out with strategies such as the "best price guarantee" and loyalty programs, demonstrating its ability to respond to consumer demands and remain relevant in the sector.

Planning

Worten's strategic planning stands out for its ability to align operations with clear and ambitious objectives. The company's mission, focused on "bringing the best of technology to everyone, without exception", reflects its commitment to accessibility and technological innovation. The vision of becoming a "one-stop shop" for the Portuguese reinforces the focus on creating a comprehensive and integrated shopping experience, combining efficiency and convenience.

The SWOT analysis carried out in the work highlights Worten's strengths, such as competitive prices and seasonal campaigns, which increase customer loyalty. The omnichannel strategy adopted by the company promotes effective integration between physical and digital channels, simplifying interaction with consumers and ensuring fluid communication between teams. This planning reflects Worten's ability to adapt to market needs and compete effectively.

Organization and Organizational Structure

Worten's organization appears to adopt a divisional structure, which is appropriate for a large company. This structure allows for better management of responsibilities, with clear departmentalization by geographic areas, products and functions. Decentralization of decisions is also a relevant characteristic, as it facilitates the speed and efficiency in solving operational problems. The profiles of the managers highlighted in the work demonstrate the high level of qualification of Worten's leadership, contributing to the effective implementation of strategies and resource management. However, the absence of an official organization chart for the company, as previously mentioned, makes it difficult to carry out a more detailed analysis of the hierarchy and the relationship between departments.

Direction

Worten applies several strategies to motivate employees, such as financial and non-financial benefits, flexible work and development opportunities. The focus on employee well-being and happiness reflects a modern approach aligned with best practices in people management.

The integration between individual and organizational objectives, evidenced by the use of target-related rewards, reinforces the company's commitment to creating a productive and motivating work environment. This attention to employee needs is a strong point that contributes to Worten's operational success.

Control

Worten's approach to organizational control is robust, integrating strategic, tactical and operational levels. The use of KPIs (key performance indicators) allows constant monitoring of progress towards defined objectives, while information systems ensure real-time data to support decision-making.

At an operational level, tools such as "Stock Management" ensure efficient inventory management, minimizing disruptions and improving customer satisfaction. However, financial control is also emphasized, with strict measures to mitigate credit risks and ensure the company's stability. These control mechanisms demonstrate Worten's ability to manage complex operations efficiently.

In short, the investment in digital platforms and omnichannel was considered an effective strategy; Product and service diversification policies, such as technical assistance, expanded the company's value proposition; and investment in targeted marketing campaigns helped to consolidate the brand's presence in the market.

We were also able to verify weaknesses in these options mentioned above, such as the lack of flexibility in some strategic areas that limits rapid responses to market changes; significant dependence on external suppliers that can generate risks in the supply chain; and little exploration of international markets, restricting expansion opportunities.

Regarding the limitations of this study, it focused mainly on the national market and did not cover a broader analysis of the sector in global contexts. Furthermore, some more up-to-date quantitative data could reinforce some of the conclusions presented.

During the course of the study, we experienced some difficulties that compromised the specificity of the work, such as obtaining specific information about the company's internal strategies, due to confidentiality. Therefore, the limited access to detailed financial data did not facilitate in-depth analyses.

Worten – An Analysis of the Organizational Structure

However, in addition to the difficulties that were eventually overcome, this project also constituted an added value for our professional future.

By carrying out the work, we were able to develop skills in strategic analysis and business management; a broader understanding of the dynamics of the technology sector; a consolidation of capabilities related to research and critical analysis of information; and greater knowledge about the chosen company, both in relation to its past and present history, its achievements, its progress and its strategies.

7. CONCLUSION

The analysis of Worten, developed throughout this work, highlights the importance of efficient and strategic management in large organizations. Through the four fundamental functions of management — planning, organization, direction and control — it was possible to understand the company's prominence in the Portuguese market.

Historical milestones and innovative strategies, such as Marketplace and omnichannel integration, demonstrate Worten's ability to adapt to market changes and consumer needs. In addition, the SWOT analysis identified significant strengths, such as competitive pricing and an effective marketing strategy, although it also highlighted challenges related to product diversity and competition.

Overall, Worten positions itself as a resilient and innovative company, but it must continue to invest in strategies to overcome external threats and consolidate its position in the market.

In short, this work served as a practical tool for applying management concepts, promoting a more critical and integrated view of the challenges faced by organizations.

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ANNEXES

Annex 1- Geographical location of the company

Annex 2 - Another tool for motivating employees: flexible working

Annex 3- Expression by Ana Luísa Gonçalves